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sharp peaks that we observe in XRD patterns reveal that the phases are well crystalline. The morphology of the prepared samples was studied through Scanning Electron Microscopy, which ensured that the compounds were well-distributed in the form of dense and inhomogeneous grain size distribution. The ac conductivity of composites increases with an increase in frequency, signifying that the conduction occurs due to slight polaron springing, and the conductivity trails the Jonschers' power law. The contribution of grain and grain boundary in the conduction mechanism is also observed from impedance spectroscopy analysis. Particular semicircular curves starting from the origin are visible in all compositions.

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Sound Chemical Management in Bangladesh: Are We Prepared to Head towards a Sustainable Chemical Industry?

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This paper will focus on establishing a framework or guideline for safe handling of chemicals which falls under the topic identified as "Chemical Management and Safe Handling". The topic is chosen because of the absence of any safety framework regarding chemical and hazardous goods handling in Bangladesh which results in the increasing number of chemical-related accidents in recent years. Since 2016, the mishandling of chemicals has caused 169 fatalities and left more than 366 people injured. The paper will propose a chemical management framework that could be applied across all industries. The paper will also review the existing laws, regulations, and conventions to identify the gaps and challenges in regard to chemical handling. Followed by an analysis of the recent major chemical-related accidents that took place in Bangladesh, to identify the areas for the recommendation. The paper will also take into account the global good practices, particularly from the developed and developing countries to provide directives for sound chemical management in a holistic and integrated manner. To prepare the framework the paper will be using primary information in the form of Key Informant Interview (KII) and existing secondary literature.

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Monitoring SDG's Indicator for Urban Built-Up Areas Expansion: A Remote Sensing Based Study on Dhaka City Corporation

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Rapid urbanization area is one of the key considerations of development of a country. Dhaka city is one of them where rapid unplanned urbanization and high population growth rate are occurring concurrently. For the proper planning and guidelines, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have

been undertaken as an endeavor by The United Nations (UN) to mitigate the regional disparity of the people across the globe. This study proposes to apply remote sensing approaches to evaluate an overall estimation of the relevant indicator SDG 11.3.1 in order to analyze the ratio of the land consumption rate (LCR) to the population growth rate (PGR) for 2000-2005, 2005-2010, 2010-2015 and 2015-2020. Besides that, Landsat 5 (TM) and 8 (OLI) satellite imageries are used to detect the built-up areas by calculating the Normalized Difference Impervious Surface Index (NDISI) and integrating population data of the same period to measure the population growth rate. The result reveals that the PGRs for the corresponding years are 0.036280, 0.03756, 0.03855, and 0.03941 percent, while the LCRs are 0.02706 and 0.0391, 0.03964, 0.04313, respectively. According to the selected indicator, the ratio of land consumption rates to the population growth rates (LCR/PGR) as per interval are 0.75, 1.04, 1.03 and 1.09. If the value of the indicator is greater than one means that the annual land consumption rate is higher than that of population growth, having this assumption in consideration, DCC is well representing the field scenarios as well.

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Utilization of Waste Iron and Waste Glass to Produce Ceramic Tiles

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Ceramic tiles are commonly used flooring material for all types of buildings such as residential, commercial or public buildings. Ceramic tiles come with a lot of benefits that make it a widely used flooring material for different buildings. Ceramic tiles are available in various designs, colors, finishes which can be used to create unique walls and floor designs. Ceramic tiles were made by mixing certain amount of Bijoypur clay, quartz and different amount of waste iron which contains higher percent (above 90) of Fe_2O_3 and K-feldspar. The samples were fired at different temperatures in the range 1075 – 1225 °C with soaking time of 1 h and the physico-mechanical and others properties were investigated. The results indicate that the combination of waste iron and K-feldspar was given comparable good results and it is used as subsidiary raw material in ceramic mixture. The use of waste iron in the standard wall and floor tiles composition decreases the firing shrinkage, increase the water absorption values and modulus of rupture.